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The Open Book Collective: Sustaining and disseminating open access books

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Abstract

This paper introduces the Open Book Collective (OBC), a new member-governed not-for-profit organization devoted to supporting the production and dissemination of Open Access Books from small-to-medium publishers. Our membership, comprised of librarians, publishers, OA service providers, and other supporters works collectively to bring about a fairer, more sustainable model of open book publishing. Though based in the UK, the collective and our membership is global. The OBC is an output of the COPIM (Community-Led Infrastructures for Open Access Books) project, an international collaboration dedicated to an equitable, diverse and sustainable future for OA books.

From our development research in collaboration with our library colleagues, we know that many libraries and institutions wish to support the publication and dissemination of OA books and indeed have a budget set aside to do so. But a confusing array of options, lack of easily readable metadata, and the varied workflow of OA publishers makes it difficult and time-consuming for libraries and their institutions to know where to invest their support. Our research then aimed to answer the question: How to build an infrastructure and platform that would simultaneously meet the needs of librarians and publishers in service of an equitable future for OA books? Between 2020 and the present, we have held workshops, hosted interactive conference presentations, networked with our stakeholders, and studied the extant literature to find answers. The OBC and its platform is the primary output of Work Package 2 of COPIM. It offers a fast and simple way for libraries to compare publishers' catalogues, packages, business plans, and values, allowing the creation of premade or bespoke subscription packages before generating a quotation. The OBC then manages the subscription, and delivers benefits to libraries including maximally readable metadata, easy integration into existing workflows, and a guarantee of quality via the vetting and application process our publisher members

must go through. We assess all membership packages on the platform, to ensure they are priced fairly and that received funding will support high quality OA publishing and distribution. The OBC is committed to supporting bibliodiversity in OA publishing. This means supporting publishers in diverse geographic and linguistic settings, while making content produced by OBC members accessible to a wider range of authors and institutions. Moreover, our model assists publishers in moving away from Book Processing Charges, which can re-entrench the inequalities already inherent in academia, leading to a stultification of fields.

Keywords: Open Access, OA Books, Sustainability, Infrastructure

Introduction

In the Global North, there have recently been some significant moves towards Open Access book publishing as a norm. Funders such as UKRI in the UK, initiatives such as Plan S in Europe, and the recent mandate from the White House all aim to make publicly funded research openly available. Such mandates do indeed support progress towards a more open landscape for books, and on the surface seem like positive changes. We should welcome them, but with caution. Large-scale moves like this do not necessarily address the pressing issues around sustainability, equity, and diversity that arise in this context of OA publishing. Fundamentally, they do not address the ongoing consolidation of research infrastructure by major publishing corporations, the encroachment of platform capitalism into OA spaces, and the ever-increasing attempts to monopolise OA publication infrastructures via horizontal and vertical integration. Such monopolistic tendencies endanger the existing diversity of OA books in language, content and form. Moreover, the reliance on Book Processing Charges which is common to major commercial players shores up the inequalities already inherent in academia.

The COPIM project, which stands for Community-Led Infrastructures for Open Access Books, is and has been an attempt to research, identify and build alternative infrastructures for OA book publication and the dissemination of OA books. Our work is built around a principle we call ‘Scaling Small’, as opposed to scaling up or out. As Adema and Moore have written:

This principle eschews standard approaches to organisational growth that tend to flatten community diversity through economies of scale. Instead, it puts forward the idea that scale can be nurtured through intentional collaborations between community-driven projects that promote a bibliodiverse ecosystem while providing resilience through resource sharing and other kinds of collaboration (2021).

In Work Package 2 specifically, our project has been to build a collective revenue and management platform for OA books that supported and enabled such a future. Our aim is antimonopolistic and anti-homogeneity. We do not seek to provide a single or centralized answer, but to create space, structures and opportunities for a diverse range of actors to flourish. We were thus faced with the question:

- How to build an infrastructure and platform that would simultaneously meet the needs of diverse librarians and publishers and service providers who are invested in of an equitable, sustainable future for OA books?

This might be broken down into a set of sub-questions including:

- What do small-to-medium OA publishers need to move away from Book Processing Charges?
- What do librarians need to make it easy, convenient and fast to gather the OA content most relevant to their institutions, and easily integrate it into their workflows?
- How do we safeguard against the incorporation and monopolization of our OA projects, as we witness multiple OA publishers and platforms being bought out by monopolies?

The major output of this work is the Open Book Collective (www.openbookcollective.com).

Methodology

The Open Book Collective has been designed and built collaboratively from its inception. In addition to desk research, our Work Package has conducted extensive outreach, discussion and workshops with small OA publishers, librarians, and infrastructure professionals. Some of the founding members of COPIM more broadly are the OA publishing collective ScholarLed, a collective of six presses founded and managed by academics, built on the same principles of Scaling Small referenced above. We have tended to divide our workshops geographically, as the needs of librarians particularly can vary depending on the funding systems of their respective countries. Reports from all our workshops can be found on our pubpub, copim.pubpub.org, by utilizing the filter 'Work Package 2', and see also the Appendix section at the end of this paper. Meanwhile, we have collaborated at every stage with Work Package 4 of COPIM (the present author is a member of both packages). Work Package 4 has utilized desk research in addition to its own workshops to explore and document better governance practices for OA infrastructures. In collaboration with Work Package 4, we have designed the governance model of the OBC, and this was also developed through a series of internal and external workshops with librarians, as well as the desk research that led to some of WP4's major outputs (see Moore 2021a; Hart and Adema 2022).

Findings and Discussion

- *What do small-to-medium OA publishers need to move away from Book Processing Charges?*

All ScholarLed Presses are committed to moving away from Book Processing Charges, and this is a condition of membership for publisher members of the OBC. This is because, as the author has written elsewhere,

[Book Processing Charges] privilege funded researchers, wealthy institutions, and established academics on permanent contracts (Nature et al., 2019, p. 14; Speicher et al., 2018). In other words, they penalise those researchers and institutions least able to bear the burden. [Our WP4 colleague] Moore (2021b) argues that expensive BPCs [...] ‘remove risk for commercial organizations wanting to publish open access while allowing them to monetize books as they have always done (Fathallah 2021).

This in turn leads away from bibliodiversity. If we continue to privilege the same institutions and academics we always have, just with an OA stamp, we do nothing to improve the breadth and diversity of scholarly output. For example, most wealthy institutions are in the Global North. For example, English is the lingua franca of academia. Angela Okune documents pressures on African academics to write and publish on matters of interest to Europe and the US specifically. Yet Ronald Snijder documents ‘significant demand for regional research and research published in languages other than English’ within the OA landscape (2022). Moving away from BPCs is a significant step in this direction.

But small-to-medium OA publishers are limited in time and humanpower, often run by just a handful of individuals alongside other academic duties. Most of them currently use piecemeal approaches to generate income, including selling paperback at low cost alongside OA digital editions and applying for grants. This of course is unpredictable and requires time and labour. They need a reliable and sustainable revenue stream - not for profit, but in order to allow them to plan and invest in future OA output. Moreover, most values-based publishers would prefer revenue streams that align with their commitment to equity and collectivism (Joy 2019; Pooley 2021).

- *What do librarians need to make it easy, convenient and fast to gather the OA content most relevant to their institutions, and easily integrate it into their workflows?*

Most university librarians are eager to support OA books in principle. Many even have budget set aside for supporting OA colleagues. But throughout our workshops and discussions, our library colleagues told us that the array of OA books on offer is confusing and can be hard to locate. Many OA books lack consistent and thorough metadata, making it hard to integrate into library workflows. Some books without a price point are invisible to the major commercial systems that categorize books, such as the Amazon and ONIX feeds. Finding OA books, assessing them for quality and relevance, and justifying purchase to budget holders is a major investment of time and labour, and librarians are working under time constraints and intensive workloads already.

- *How do we safeguard against the incorporation and monopolization of our OA projects, as we witness multiple OA publishers and platforms being bought out by monopolies?*

This is an issue several of our publisher colleagues have written passionately on (Pooley 2021; Joy 2019), as have our colleagues at COPIM (COPIM 2021). The years 2017-2022 have seen the acquisition of multiple OA initiatives by major corporations, including Knowledge Unlatched by Wiley; bepress by Elsevier; F1000 Research by Taylor & Francis and Ubiquity by De Gruyter. Jeff Pooley, director of mediastudies.press has argued that ‘the scholarly

communication ecosystem should aim not only to be open but non-profit too' because 'the profit motive is fundamentally misaligned with core values of academic life, potentially corroding ideals like unfettered inquiry, knowledge-sharing, and cooperative progress'. He goes on to argue that the 'non-profit, scholar-run' governance structures can act as a safeguard against these takeovers. The initiatives which were acquired were not protect by their governance charters. In collaboration with Work Package 4 and external colleagues from all stakeholder groups, we have designed governance model for the OBC to protect against this and to guarantee its non-profit status. Of course, this is not the single answer to reclaiming academic publishing as a public good, but it does offer an alternative to monopolies presently dominant.

Outcome: The Open Book Collective

The Open Book Collective is a nonprofit organization registered in England and Wales, presently in the process of becoming a charity. Whilst incorporating as a charity has always been our aim, the legal processes to accomplish this are quite extensive, and take time. The Open Book Collective is comprised of three types of members: small-to-medium OA publishers, OA infrastructure service providers, and libraries. Our members work together to bring about a fairer, more equitable and more sustainable model of open book publishing. The OBC is founded on a set of key values, which are written into our governance charter:

- the care and curation of high-quality academic books;
- a commitment to bibliodiversity;
- collaboration and resource-sharing over competition;
- networked community-building over profit-driven centralization;
- horizontal working relationships over exclusive hierarchisation; and
- growing and safeguarding open accessibility to, and reuse of, academic books for global readers without technical or economic barriers.

The Open Book Collective platform can be found at openbookcollective.org. Through this platform, our publishers and service providers offer individual and collective membership packages which libraries pay to join. After comparing the packages on offer, library members may select one or create a bespoke package according to the priorities of their institution. The platform then generates a quotation, which as part of our commitment to equity, is tiered according to the size of the library or institution. The quotation is not set in stone - OBC staff will discuss this quotation with the library or supporter before it is finalized. Once agreed, the platform generates a contract, and the OBC manages the revenue stream, including via third party arrangements.

For our publisher members, this provides an equitable, sustainable and predictable revenue stream according to which they can plan for the future. In accordance with our charitable objectives, revenue gathered through the OBC

may only be used in the production of OA books. In addition to the financial support, OBC publishers benefit from the opportunity network and collaborate with likeminded ventures; save labour on outreach; and can avail themselves of the collective knowledge and experience of the OBC members collectively.

For our library members, the OBC likewise addresses many of the issues they have in supporting OA. Firstly, the OBC serves as a guarantee of quality for OA books. Our publisher members must meet membership criteria before acceptance which assures the high quality of their output. These criteria include high standards for peer review of submitted manuscripts and comprehensive, maximally readable metadata. Secondly, the OBC platform is massively time and labour saving for librarians, allowing them to rapidly compare the output, values, missions and operating procedures of a range of high-quality OA publishers and select and/or create a package that aligns with the priorities of their institution. This in turn makes it easy to demonstrate value to budget holders, and eases the incorporation of OA content into library workflows.

The OBC's governance structure has been specifically designed to safeguard and preserve its values, and particularly to guard against incorporation. The full document is publicly available (see Joy, Adema & COPIM 2022), but we will pull out a few points here. Firstly, the fact that the OBC is in the process of becoming a charity means that it cannot be acquired for profit, and must abide by its charitable objectives for the promotion of public good. We have chosen to incorporate as an Association model, meaning that the Trustees are members of the charity, as opposed to an external board. It also means that the broader membership has voting power, as opposed to the trustees only. In accordance with our values, the OBC self-defines as a 'community-led and membership-driven organisation' (Joy, Adema & COPIM 2022). When members join, they become part of the General Assembly of Custodians (GAC). We chose the word Custodians specifically to reference the role of safeguarding the OBC and its values. They may choose to be Full Custodians, and thus be entitled to vote and expected to attend the AGM, or Associate Custodians, which effectively opts them out of the governance structure, though Associates may change to Full Custodians at any time and vice versa. Members belong to one of three caucuses, i.e., libraries, publishers, and OA service providers. The other governance bodies are the Board of Stewards (BoS), voted on by the GAC, the Membership Committee (MC), and the Secretariat. Figure 1 shows the structure of the OBC governance model:

Figure 1: OBC Governance Model

The BoS is the primary management body of the OBC. It will be made up of 9 members: 2 each elected from the caucuses of publishers, libraries, and service providers, and 3 OA experts, nominated by the BoS and Full Custodians and elected by the Full Custodians. We have designed this structure carefully to represent the balance of interests amongst members and ensure that no caucus takes priority. One theme that consistently emerged from our stakeholder workshops was the fact that, whilst it might be comfortable to think of ourselves as a holistic ‘OA Community’, individual members ultimately have different needs, powers and degrees of agency. To ignore the potential for conflict would be as Chantal Mouffe put it, ‘an evasion of the political’ (1993, 2). Or as the author wrote previously in a reflection on the process:

How should a collective be governed? This was the question that punctum books’ Director Eileen Joy and I took the lead in addressing, in collaboration with our COPIM colleagues and a range of workshop participants. The terms of the question seem almost contradictory: a ‘collective’ implies equity, collegiality, co-operation and a lack of organized hierarchy, whilst ‘governed’ suggests top-down management structures, or the imposition of rules and regulations by a select group over a larger majority [...] we needed to find a way that the different groups of

stakeholders could be effectively organized to work together and get the most out of the platform in a mutually beneficial arrangement (Fathallah 2021).

As the name suggests, the membership committee is a sub-committee elected from the Board of Stewards to assess and makes decisions about incoming membership applications. It sets and oversees the criteria for presses and publishing service providers who would like to join the OBC (ratified by the BoS). The whole of the governance structure is supported by the Secretariat, whilst the Management team is responsible for the day-to-day running of the platform and organization.

Conclusion

In their Principles for Open Scholarly Infrastructures, Bilder, Lin and Neylon wrote that ‘Everything we have gained by opening content and data will be under threat if we allow the enclosure of scholarly infrastructures’ (2015). Unfortunately, since the publication of these principles in 2015, the enclosure of open infrastructures and the acquisition of OA publishers by major corporates proceeds apace. This weakens and homogenizes the OA landscape, and further entrenches the dominance of Book Processing Charges which penalise academics from less privileged institutions, biasing the field of publication toward those already in stable employment at wealthy universities. Meanwhile, most librarians want to support OA, but they are overwhelmed by the choice of content available, the lack of metadata, and the difficulties involved in justifying purchases to budget holders. The OBC is an intervention we arrived at, through a collaborative process of workshopping with stakeholders in addition to desk research, that aims to serve both theoretical, values-based and practical needs within the OA landscape. Going forward, we will seek to diversify our operations, promoting and supporting a more global readership and set of member publishers. We also seek to enhance the services we can offer our members, both through charitable grants and the provision of free tool-kits and advice for OA publishers, libraries and infrastructure providers that align with our vision and values.

Disclosure statement

The author has been a member of the COPIM project since 2020, and is part of Work Packages 2 and 4. The COPIM project is funded by Research England and Arcadia.

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Appendix

Please see the following for further information:

- The COPIM project website: <https://www.copim.ac.uk/>
- The COPIM project pubpub (open ocumentation site): <https://copim.pubpub.org/>
- All COPIM outputs at Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/copim?page=1&size=20> The Open Book Collective platform: <http://openbookcollective.org>
- The Open Book Collective Information Hub at pubpub: <https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/>

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